

THE TERM OF “COMPETENCY” IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. *Improving the lexical competence of pedagogues in learning foreign languages, speaking fluently in a foreign language, being able to express one's opinion freely, the ability to think creatively, to work independently by getting to know the original foreign literature, to inform the recruiting requirements of professors and teachers in the field and systematic work is being carried out to ensure that they have high competence, working intensively in communication conditions.*

Keywords: *competency, definition, education, the types of competency.*

Acquisition of foreign languages in accordance with international qualification requirements in world educational and scientific research institutions, improvement of competitive pedagogical personnel system and innovative educational technologies, training of competent teachers based on the requirements of pan-European CEFR standards, improvement of lexical competence of teachers based on an integrative approach scientific research is being carried out. At the same time, in the course of professional development, special attention is paid to scientific research on the development of lexical, grammatical and speech competence of pedagogues, the formation of phraseological competence, and the expansion of linguo-didactic possibilities of foreign language teaching.

In recent years, in the field of teaching foreign languages in our republic, in the continuous educational chain of "school-higher educational institution-enterprise", learning a language suitable for all layers of the population, improving lexical skills based on sets of exercises The foundations are being created. "50% of teachers of vocational subjects (except foreign language) working in state higher education institutions should have at least B2 level national or equivalent international certificate"[1] as a priority. As a result, opportunities for improving the lexical competence of teachers in the process of professional development increased.

Competence is a broad concept, its content and essence are interpreted differently by scientists. Many interpretations of the terms "competence" and "competence" have been given in foreign studies. For example, R. Jakendoff says, "competence or knowledge in this field" [2]. "Competence" (Latin: compete-reach, match, match) refers to the authority given to a specific organization or a person in a position by a law, regulation or other document.

J. Winterton and D. Delamare-Le [3] competence is the standard behavior and behavior required by a certain activity, and competence is the degree of compliance with this requirement (standard), that is, the final result of demonstrating competence. - they describe it.

A. Verbisky [108] and O. Iskanderova [4] "competence" is a person's goals, values, motives, personal qualities, knowledge, skills, skills, abilities and experiences that ensure the implementation of this or that activity.

This concept entered our republic's education system in the early 1990s. By specialists, it is called differently, for example, by J. Jalolov [5], and T. Sattorov [6] by concepts such as "factor",

"skill" in the sources reflecting the theory and history of pedagogy. Below are the definitions given by the scientists of our country.

According to the "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan": "competency (lat. *competo* - I achieve, I am worthy, I am worthy) means that a certain state body (local self-governing body) or an official has a law, regulation or scope of powers, rights and duties defined by another document; It means knowledge and experience in this or that field" [7]. Summarizing the above descriptions, competence is a combination of various interrelated abilities and characteristics of a person, necessary for effective work in a certain field.

The "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" defines this term as follows: "competency (from Latin *competere*- to be worthy) is the range of powers of a specific body or official, defined in official documents, authority; it is a person's awareness of a certain field, the level of knowledge in this field"[70]. Competence is the manifestation of the algorithm that ensures productivity through human capabilities, and the activity of the human being as a specialist, directed to the goal and fully manifesting his capabilities.

According to B.Kh.Khodjaev [8], competence is the ability to use acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in everyday and professional activities.

According to K.J.Riskulova [9], "competence" means professional laws, principles, requirements, rules, duty, duties and obligations, as well as a set of personal deontological norms, necessary for the owner of this or that profession. Competence is the ability to demonstrate competence standards based on creativity based on the demands of society, depending on the practical activity of the individual. The main criterion of competence is determined by effective activity, training of competitive personnel.

In contrast to the knowledge that exists in organizing the results of a person's cognitive activity, in the display of concepts and ideas, competence is determined only in practice. In general, competence is the practical application of existing knowledge, skills, and abilities, the ability to provide lacking knowledge, and the result of necessary knowledge, skills, and abilities characterized by the manifestation of one's own capabilities.

The following traditional classifications of competencies are noted in the scientific-methodical literature:

- political and social competencies related to the ability to take responsibility, participate in decision-making in cooperation;

- competencies encountered in the life of society, aimed at living with other people regardless of culture, language and religion, understanding them, helping them and resolving mutual conflicts;

- descriptive competencies of written and oral communication, which are important in professional activity and community life;

- competencies related to the emergence of the information society (acquiring new technologies and determining their advantages and disadvantages).

Based on this, there are two main types of competencies in the educational process: divided into basic and special competencies. Basic competences are the ability to engage in personal, social, economic and professional relationships, to take one's place in society, to solve the problems encountered, and most importantly, to be competitive in one's field and profession. It is focused on the composition of skills. They are divided into the following types: competences such

as communicative, working with information, self-development as a person, socially active citizen, universal, mathematical literacy [10].

Professor N. Muslimov shares the opinion that in the process of mastering each academic subject, special competences in education are competences relevant to the field, based on the specifics and content of the subject. In particular, the formation of speech, linguistic, lexical, social-cultural or discourse and strategic competencies is required in learning English.

It should be noted that basic and special competences are interdependent and will produce effective results only if they are formed while complementing each other. In the conditions of intense globalization and market relations, being able to withstand the strong competition that takes priority in the labor market requires every specialist to have professional competence and to increase it in a consistent manner. If we turned to the essence of the concept of "competence" above, now it is the turn of the concept of "competence". In the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, the term competence is derived from the Latin word "compete" and is defined as meaning "I achieve", "I am eligible", and according to A. Belkin's explanation, it means He shows that he has knowledge, knowledge and experience in all fields. In particular, G. Garfinkel the knowledge, skills and experiences of a competent person, social-professional, i.e. suitability for the professional position he occupies in society, performance of the duties of his position, he understands that he is capable of solving problems. From his reasoning in this regard, it is assumed that a competent person has certain knowledge and skills and effective work in this or that situation.

As we mentioned above, N. Muslimov stated that the concept of "competence" entered the field of science and education as a result of psychological research. Therefore, the competence is "how the specialist behaves in non-traditional situations, in unexpected situations, to communicate, to take a new approach in relations with competitors, to perform ambiguous tasks, to use information full of conflicts, to develop rationality and "Having a plan of action in complex processes" means. Competence is used as a descriptive characteristic of specific activity requirements for the subject of labor or the attitude of the subject to the specific aspects of specific activity of the subject. In this regard, R.P.Milrud noted: "Competence began to be studied in the form of a personal category, and competences became curriculum components, and the anatomy of competences was organized". So, the concept of "competence" indicates not only having a certain ability, but also a personal attitude towards this type of activity. That is, a competent person in a certain field must have appropriate knowledge and skills to have a reasonable opinion about this field and to carry out effective activities in it.

In linguistics, the term "competence" was introduced by the American scientist N. Chomsky in the middle of the 20th century, and the term "language competence" was used in the semantic opposite of the term "language use".

But for the first time, this term was described as being used by the Scottish scholar J. Raven in the 1590s in Webster's Online Dictionary ("Competence" was first used in popular English literature: sometime before 1590).

The difference between these terms is the knowledge of the language of the "speaking person and the listening person" and the level of its use in practice, i.e. in speech activity. By the 70s of the last century, the followers of N.Chomsky [10] defined it as the potential knowledge of the language and the knowledge of the language of the real language owner, i.e. language competence, and its use in real speech in any authentic situations, i.e. "language activity". " start

to be interpreted as concepts. D.Slobin and Dj.Grın [11] clearly explained the meaning of these concepts and they emphasized that "a person can communicate in practice, that is, in any specific situation, only if he has the ability to speak and understand from a theoretical point of view". In a short period of time, these views caused the emergence of the concept of "competence" due to the passage of time, i.e. development. This, in turn, caused the emergence of the terms "lexical competence", "strategic competence", "discourse competence", "communicative competence". Over time, in addition to these, the concept of "competencies" appeared.

The term "competence" was adopted in 1996 in the context of research on communication-oriented education conducted by the Council of Europe in Strasbourg to determine the level of foreign language acquisition. At that time, "competence" was defined as the ability to perform some activity based on the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired during training.

J. Jalolov defined "competence" as trying to learn a language, being able to learn a language.

Today, the word competence means ability, competent ability, and competence and competence in education are education aimed at forming the ability to apply acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications in personal, professional and social activities. don't understand in fact, a competent approach to language education is the ability of students to use the language materials they learn and the information they receive in their life activities, to express their thoughts independently orally and in writing, and to develop lexical skills in adapting to speech situations. It consists of the formation of application skills, that is, the formation of the ability to use the language in a purposeful way.

From this point of view, one of the indicators of the quality of education is considered competent. Competence is described not only as a combination of knowledge and skills, but also as the ability to mobilize the acquired knowledge and apply it in practice in specific situations [12].

In order for a person to be able to engage in personal, social, economic and professional relationships, to take his place in society, to solve the problems that he faces, to have a broad worldview and knowledge in all aspects, first of all, it is necessary to integrate the teaching of sciences, In order to engage in mutual communication, it is necessary to master a foreign language and improve the competence to use it effectively in communication.

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